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HAND MOTION CLASSIFIER USING BIOMIMETIC PATTERN RECOGNITION WITH CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORKS WITH A DYNAMIC THRESHOLD METHOD FOR MOTION EXTRACTION USING EF SENSORS

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Abstract: In this paper, we propose a Biometric Pattern Recognition (BPR) with Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) motion classifier for a hand motion classification as well as a dynamic thresholding algorithm for motion signal extraction by Electric Field (EF) sensors. We developed a motion detection algorithm using a dynamic threshold method to overcome uncertainty in the initial electrostatic charge state of the sensor affected by a user and his/her surrounding environment. This method can detect the hand motion and extract its motion signal frame effectively with high accuracy.

Keywords: Biometric Pattern Recognition (BPR), Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN), motion signal, electric potential signal, dynamic thresholding method, different signal, optimal separating, hand motion.

Introduction

The EF sensor detects changes in the electric field around the sensor and outputs an analogue capacitance voltage value. EF (Electric Field) sensor can often be divided to two modes in terms of its usage; contact mode and non-contact mode. The contact type is mainly used for healthcare or medical applications by sensing bioelectric signals such as electrocardiogram, electromyogram, and electroencephalogram. Meanwhile, in the non- contact type, electric potential signal can be measured due to change in the electric charges on surface of EF sensors caused by human body or hand movement [1-3].

Using EF sensors, human body detection is possible up to 3 to 4 meters away in all directions, motion recognition is possible by penetrating obstacles, and it is suitable to support the weakness of image recognition because it does not require light or voice. It has been confirmed that EF sensors can now obtain various forms of hand

gestures through the multi-channel sensor input plate and can distinguish among acquired patterns [4-5].

In this paper, we present hand-motion detection and classification system using a BPR CNN classifier combined with a dynamic threshold method for automatic motion detection and motion-frame extraction (Fig 1).

Figure 1. Motion detection and frame extraction process

Discussion

1. Dynamic offset and thresholding

One of the challenging problems in dynamic thresholding method for signal detection and frame extraction is to determine an offset voltage for each EPS and then adjust threshold values periodically (typically in every second) before detecting a motion because each sensor starts with different initial offset according to different environmental situation time by time. EPS sensor has another important characteristic that produces a similar signal pattern for a similar motion even though the signal level or offset varies in time. That is the reason that our method can maintain the robustness regardless of time-variant offset value. As shown in Fig. 2, EPS sensor’s typical output signal repeats up and down states. So we can catch a motion by using two threshold values.

2. Motion detection and extraction

In order to detect different signal patterns resulted by different motion speed and size, distance, and direction according to motion, and also to extract correct motion signal frames we take into account duration, motion end points final motion frame can be determined by the adding an additional 10% of the range initial extracted frame. Figure 2 shows a process in which motion detection and frames are automatically performed in real time using a dynamic threshold in a typical hand motion. Initial threshold can be extracted based on new threshold values updated at measurement time.

Figure 2. A typical extracted motion frame

10% of the initial frames range added to begin to make a final frame because most real motion and end before/after the threshold line point as shown in Figure 2 are taken in our proposed method:

3. BPR-CNN classifier

Biomimetic Pattern Recognition (BPR) is a new model of pattern recognition, which is based on “matter cognition” instead of “matter classification.” This new model is much closer to the recognition function of human beings, who cognize matters class by class, than traditional statistical pattern recognition using “optimal separating” as its main principle. In the BPR, “cognizing” one class of matters is essential to analyzing and “cognizing” the shape of infinite points set made up of all samples of the same class. We use, new method that combines CNNs with BPR is proposed to reduce the complexity of training networks and to improve the performance of classification. Because CNNs represent an inspiration of the cognitive neuroscience while BPR implies the cognitive psychology, it is reasonable to combine them together in the framework of cognitive science. In our framework, CNNs are used to automatically learn feature vectors from raw images, and then the learned feature vectors are projected into high-dimensional space to be covered by BPR classifier. Figure 5 shows the structure proposed for our BPR-CNN.

Figure 5. Structure of BPR-CNN proposed

For our BPR-CNN, the input layer is followed by a convolutional layer C1 with 5×5 filters and 6 maps of size 60×60 . The subsequent max-pooling layer P1 reduces the previous layer size to 30×30 by 2×2 filters. Convolutional layer C2 with 5×5 filters and 12 maps of size 24×24 . The subsequent max-pooling layer P2 reduces the previous layer size to 12×12 by 2×2 filters. C3 also employs 3×3 filters but has 24 maps with dimensions of 8×8 pixels. P3 with 2×2 pooling windows yields 12×12

feature maps that are fully connected to $12 \times 4 = 48$ hidden neurons. These 48 hidden neurons are finally connected to the 4 output units.

Because the CNN is employed as an automatic feature extractor and BPR as a classifier in our proposed method, after training for 20 epochs with a learning rate of 0.1, the fully connected layer with dimensions of 48 is projected into the feature space.

In this study, our dynamic thresholding method and a CNN-BPR combined model for image classification is proposed. The proposed model treats CNN as a feature extractor, which can automatically learn the feature representation. BPR is adept in providing an accurate classifier. Our proposed methods are targeted for use to mobile systems with non-contact mode EF sensors based. In this study, a dynamic threshold scheme was used to extract the wanted signal only, caused by hand motion near the sensor. Our automatic motion extraction and classification method demonstrates its high performance in terms of accuracy. Our study will be further developed toward future development for a gesture controlled smart mobile system using EF sensors.

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